

ALTERNATING CURRENT ELECTROLYSIS. PART VII. OSCILLOGRAPHIC STUDY OF POTENTIAL VARIATIONS AT A PLATINUM ELECTRODE IN SULPHURIC ACID

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A study of current-voltage characteristics and voltage-time curves during A. C. electrolysis has been presented. The voltage-time curves obtained show that during the anodic half-cycle, the processes taking place are (i) desorption and ionisation of previously adsorbed hydrogen, (ii) charging of electrode double layer and (iii) the formation of a film of PtO of one molecule thickness leading to the steady evolution of oxygen. The cathodic half-cycle consists of several stages, representing the (a) charging of double layer (b) the reduction of oxide and (c) formation of a monatomic layer of hydrogen atoms on the electrode leading to a steady oxygen evolution. At higher frequencies of alternation, the potential does not reach the value corresponding to the hydrogen or oxygen evolution value.

Chemical effects produced by symmetrical alternating current between platinum electrodes in sulphuric acid solutions have been reported in a previous investigation (Part III, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 278). If during A. C. electrolysis, the polarised platinum electrode and a stationary reversible electrode, kept in the same solutions, are connected to the Y-plates of an oscillograph, using time base, the trace obtained on the screen will represent voltage-time relation at the electrode during an entire cycle. A study of these curves as well as current-voltage characteristics of an electrode during A. C. electrolysis is presented in this communication.

Bowden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, 125 A, 446) found an almost linear relation between electrode voltage and quantity of electricity passed when a platinum electrode was changed from cathodic to anodic polarisation. In addition, some arrests were observed on the curve which were attributed to the depolarisation of hydrogen and reduction of platinum oxide during the anodic and cathodic voltage build-up respectively. The anodic process was found to be the removal of adsorbed hydrogen and the formation of an adsorbed layer of oxygen atoms. Butler and Armstrong (*ibid.*, 1932, 137A, 604) observed that prior to the evolution of oxygen, entire surface of the electrode was covered with an envelope of oxygen atoms. These workers further reported that the initial process, when a hydrogen-evolving electrode was changed to oxygen-evolving one, was the ionisation of adsorbed hydrogen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 743). Pearson and Butler (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 1163) detected three stages during anodic polarisation of platinum electrode, considered to be due to: (1) removal of adsorbed hydrogen, (2) charging of electrode double layer, and (3) deposition of monatomic layer of oxygen leading to a steady oxygen evolution. The cathodic polarisation curve also contained the same three stages. Hickling (*ibid.*, 1945, 41, 333) confirmed these observations. However, Hickling suggests that before a steady evolution of oxygen can occur, adsorption of oxygen dipoles on the electrode leading to the formation of platinum oxide may occur.

Thus, from the literature we find that the steady evolution of oxygen or hydrogen at a platinum electrode is preceded by several other processes. Since, in the present

case, an electrode is subjected to A. C. polarisation, a study of voltage-time curves will provide an idea of the different processes taking place when an electrode, evolving oxygen, is changed to hydrogen-evolving one, and *vice versa*.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement used is shown in Fig. 1. The polarising current was taken from circuit ABC where C was the rotating commutator. The A. C. was fed to two polished platinum electrodes dipping in H_2SO_4 solution. E was standard half cell- $Hg/Hg_2SO_4 \cdot M/2 \cdot K_2SO_4$ -placed in a vessel F containing $M/2 \cdot K_2SO_4$ and contact with the electrode was made through a Luggin capillary. The voltage between the platinum electrode and reference electrode was fed through D. C. amplifiers to the Y-plates of a cathode ray oscillograph. The Y-deflection on the screen was calibrated by means of the potentiometer P.

FIG. 1

The oscillograms were photographed with a 'Du Mont camera'; the O-voltage trace as well as the oscillograph screen was also photographed on the same film for reference.

Luggin Capillary Adjustment.—It was found that as the capillary tip was moved away from the electrode, the peak to peak voltage of the trace appearing on the C.R.O. screen increased. The capillary tip was therefore pushed towards the electrode till the peak to peak voltage was minimum and there was no voltage drop at the cut-off taking place between the positive and negative half-cycles. This is shown in Fig. 2(a) which shows the trace when the capillary tip is slightly away from the electrode surface. Fig. 2(b) shows the change in the waveform when the tip is touching the electrode. To decrease the IR drop between the capillary tip and the electrode, K_2SO_4 was added to the electrolyte so that it was $M/2$ with respect to K_2SO_4 .

Current-voltage measurements were done by gradually increasing the current, the peak to peak voltage being measured on the calibrated oscillograph screen as the trace appeared on it. The position of the O-voltage trace being known, the peak voltage above this line affords the maximum potential during the cathodic cycle and below it gives the maximum potential during the anodic cycle. Knowing the potential of the half cell, the maximum anodic and cathodic potential during the entire cycle can be calculated. These results are plotted at different values of frequency of alternation (Figs. 3 and 4). All the voltages recorded are on hydrogen scale.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

Potential-time Curves.—As the current is increased, the potential-time wave-form as appears on the C.R.O. screen also varies. At lower values of current strength, the wave-form is logarithmic in each half-cycle (Fig. 5a). On increasing the current, the wave-form has the shape shown in Fig. 5b. At this stage, it will be seen that the voltage during cathodic half-cycle abruptly falls to a value of +0.65 v, then slowly becomes more negative, then rapidly falls linearly with time. The anodic half-cycle also shows a rapid rise of potential to a value of +0.65 v. Beyond this value, the voltage rises linearly with time. On increasing the current

Fig. 5a.

Fig. 5b.

Fig. 5c.

Fig. 5d.

further (Fig. 5c), the anodic curve is seen to rise slowly in the initial stages, then rapidly to a value of 0.85 v; the cathodic curve also shows a similar kink at a voltage of +0.35 v. At a still higher current strength, the curve shape is nearly retained, but the anodic curve is seen to flatten out; there is a similar flattening observed in the cathodic curve also (Fig. 5d). This stage corresponds to visible gas evolution at the electrode and the maximum negative potential (peak value) during cathodic cycle is 0.03 v, which corresponds to the hydrogen overvoltage value at platinum. Beyond this stage, increase in current strength increases the length of the flat top in both the half-cycles. It is significant to note that during the anodic voltage build-up, the voltage continues to be that of hydrogen evolution value during the first few microseconds. Such a behaviour is not obtained during cathode voltage build-up.

From an examination of the current-voltage curves, it can be seen that during cathodic discharge, at low frequencies, the voltage rises slowly at first, then rapidly and finally reaches a constant value corresponding to hydrogen evolution. This curve is very much similar to the C × V curves obtained in D. C. electrolysis except for the slow rise of potential in the initial stages. At higher frequencies, the shape of the curve is essentially the same except for the fact that the initial slow rise of potential is more prominent and the voltage does not reach the hydrogen evolution value even at high current strength. At higher frequencies, a break at a voltage value of +0.25 v is obtained. The anodic curve shows a break at +1.07 v at higher values of frequency.

An examination of the voltage-time curves, obtained at a stage when gas evolution is taking place at the electrode, shows that the anodic curve contains five distinct stages (Fig. 5d). The initial stages 'a' and 'b' are obviously due to the presence of adsorbed hydrogen on the electrode since the potential at 'a' corresponds to the H-overvoltage value. The stage 'b', where the potential rises linearly with time, may be due to the ionisation of adsorbed hydrogen. These stages have been reported by Pearson and Butler (*loc. cit.*). The number of coulombs contained in stages 'a' and 'b' are 120 and 300 microcoulombs per sq. cm. of electrode surface. The total number of coulombs contained in both these stages corresponds to the value, reported by Hickling (*loc. cit.*), for the desorption and ionisation of adsorbed hydrogen during anode voltage build-up. The stage 'c' is due to the charging of the double layer as the length of this stage has not been found to be affected by electrode poisons. This is further substantiated by the fact that the potential of a static platinum electrode in the same electrolyte is the same as that obtained at the end of the stage 'c'.

The stage 'd' commences at a potential of +0.82 v. The potential of Pt/PtO in 2N-H₂SO₄ has been shown by Grube to be 0.9 v (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1910, 16, 621). Hence, it is likely that this stage may be due to the commencement of the formation of an oxide layer on the electrode. This stage is found to contain 900 microcoulombs per apparent sq. cm. of electrode surface. These would liberate 1.4×10^{18} molecules or 2.8×10^{15} atoms of oxygen. Since there are approximately 1.6×10^{18} atoms of platinum per sq. cm.

of electrode surface and as the true area can be considered to be about twice the apparent area, this stage corresponds to the formation of a monatomic layer of oxygen atoms, completely covering the electrode surface. Alternatively, it can be assumed that the formation of PtO takes place at the electrode during this stage, the thickness of the oxide layer being of one molecule. The voltage build-up curve during the cathodic half-cycle shows a break at a voltage corresponding to the reduction of PtO formed previously. However, it is observed that the anode voltage build-up curve does not 'stay' at the voltage corresponding to the formation of the oxide; on the contrary, the voltage rises linearly with time. Hickling (*loc. cit.*) suggests the adsorption of oxygen dipoles on the electrode resulting in the formation of an unstable 'species' reacting rapidly to form PtO.

The cathodic voltage build-up curve consists of an initial stage 'A' corresponding to the charging of electrode double layer. It is significant to note that the lengths of this stage and the anodic stage 'c' are the same. This stage is followed by stage 'B' during which the voltage 'stays' at a voltage of +0.65 v. This stage is found to contain 500 microcoulombs. The stage is therefore probably due to the presence of PtO on the electrode surface, the reduction of the oxide taking place at a more negative potential than that required for its formation. After this stage the potential again rises rapidly till the deposition of hydrogen atoms takes place. This stage 'C' contains 500 microcoulombs which results in the deposition of 3.2×10^{13} atoms of hydrogen on the electrode surface. Taking into account the fact that some of the hydrogen may diffuse into the metal, it is apparent that the steady evolution of hydrogen is preceded by the formation of an envelope of hydrogen atoms on the electrode. This is in conformity with the observations of previous workers (*loc. cit.*).

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